

Influence of socioeconomic status on blood pressure among teenagers in Kano State, Nigeria

Saratu Umar Aliyu¹_{A-F}, Farida Garba Sumaila²_{A-F},

1- Department of Physiotherapy, Rasheed Shekoni Specialist Hospital Dutse, Jigawa State, Nigeria.

2- Department of Physiotherapy, Bayero University Kano, Kano State, Nigeria.

Received: November 17, 2016; Accepted: November 27, 2016

Abstract

This study investigated the influence of socioeconomic status (SES) on blood pressure (BP) among teenagers in Kano state. A cross-sectional research design was used for the study. A total of five hundred and twenty teenage students of ages 13 – 19 years were randomly selected from twelve (12) public secondary schools in Kano state. Weight, height, and BP of all the subjects were taken using weighing scale, calibrated wall meter, and mercury sphygmomanometer respectively. SES information of all the subjects was obtained through SES specific questionnaire. Scores were assigned to each question in the questionnaire based on their status symbol. Based on the scores obtained from the questionnaire, subjects were categorized to low SES class (30.2%), middle SES class (62.7%), and high SES class (7.1%). Data collected was summarized using descriptive statistics and was analyzed using inferential statistics of Pearson product moment correlation, one-way ANOVA and Scheffe post-hoc at an alpha level of 0.05 with statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 15.

The results of the study shows a significant influence of SES on systolic BP (SBP) ($F_{2, 517} = 5.290, P < 0.05$), and no significant influence of SES on diastolic BP (DBP) ($F_{2, 517} = 2.091, P > 0.05$). Scheffe post-hoc was computed across the SES classes and their mean SBP, and found a significant mean difference between low SES and high SES ($MD = 6.306, P < 0.05$), and between middle SES and high SES ($MD = 7.055, P < 0.05$). A non significant relationship between SES and SBP ($r = -0.062, P > 0.05$), and between SES and DBP ($r = 0.004, P > 0.05$) was found. The study therefore recommended that SES should be considered while assessing teenage patients.

Keywords: Work related musculoskeletal pains (WRMSP), Work related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSD), commercial tricycle drivers (CTDs), pattern.

Introduction

Blood pressure (BP) also referred to as arterial blood pressure, is the pressure exerted by circulating blood upon the walls of blood vessels [1]. High blood pressure (HBP) is a sustained systolic blood pressure (SBP) of greater than or equals to 140mmHg or sustained diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of greater than or equals to 90mmHg [2]. Worldwide, HBP or hypertension is now regarded as a “silent killer” and a major public health problem [3] that complicates other diseases as well as increases surgical risk and disturbs growing adolescent [4]. HBP is the leading risk factor for stroke, cardiovascular diseases, renal disease, and death [5]; and it depends on other factors like alcohol drinking, obesity, and sedentary life style [6]. These risk factors have been reported [6, 7, 8] to differ according to social status.

HBP is classified based on SBP and DBP. If SBP or DBP measurement is higher than the accepted values for the age of the individual its considered as pre-hypertension or hypertension [9]. It has been explained that, it is easier to diagnosed HBP in children by considering their age, gender, and height percentile [10]. In a study

by Balogun, Obajuluwa, Olaogun, and Aberejojo on children between the age of 8 and 20, they found the 95th percentile BP of the children to be 133/92mmHg, and they postulated that Nigerian children with sustained BP greater than or equals to 133/92mmHg should be considered hypertensive [11].

It has been reported that hypertension has changed from a minor cause of mortality and disability to a major cause of diseases worldwide [12]. Also, an increase in the prevalence of hypertension in developed countries from 2000 to 2006 has been documented [5]. In Nigeria, high prevalence of hypertension was reported in Ibadan, Lagos, Enugu, and Kano [13, 14]. In Kano, there is high rate of hypertension and high level of plasma cholesterol in teenagers [14].

Socioeconomic status (SES) refers to components of economic and social status that categorized people based on wealth, income, expenditure, education, and housing conditions [13]. Pattern of association between SES and health differs in developed and less developed countries. Van Rossum et al explained that in developed countries, cardiovascular risk factors are more prevalent

in the lower SES class, and more prevalent in high SES class in less developed countries [8]. Several modifiable SES determinants like occupation and education, urban and rural dwelling, local or national economic conditions, are all associated with hypertension but the way they associates is somewhat complicated and contradictory [16]. For instance, in a study by Akinkugbe et al where they compare the BP of black and white Americans children with Nigerian children, they reported consistently higher systolic and diastolic BP in Nigerian children than on the black and white Americans, and they postulated that the differences in the BP is due to environmental factors than to genetic factors [17]. Another study by Oviasu, Alakija and Oyarebu where they compared the BP of Nigerian children living in urban and rural areas, and they found that both the systolic and diastolic BP of the children living in towns were consistently higher than those living in rural, and they attributed the differences in the BP between the two groups to environmental factors and fitness level [18].

Materials and Methods

A total of 520 male and female teenage students between 13 to 19 years from selected public schools in Kano state participated in the cross sectional study.

Data Collection Instruments

- Mercury sphygmomanometer : KBK SM-300 (made in Japan) was used to measure blood pressure in mmHg.
- Height scale: Calibrated wall meter was used to measure height in meters (m).
- Weight scale: Orbit bathroom scale (model: supreme, serial number 0399104033) was used to measure weight in kilograms (kg).
- Socioeconomic status questionnaire: This was used to determine the SES information. The questionnaire was adopted from Balogun et al, (1990) and modified. The questionnaire was validated and its reliability (0.87) was ascertained by conducting a pilot study using fifty (50) teenagers (13 to 19 years from public secondary school in Kano). The questionnaire consists of two sections; section A

required the demographic data of the participants, and section B required information of the participants and their parents/guardians. The questionnaires seek information on education, income, health status, land and physical properties. Scores were assigned to each question based on their status symbol, with a minimum score of 0 and maximum score of 57. Teenagers with score 0 – 18 were classified as low SES, those with scores 19-39 were classified as middle SES, and those with scores above 40 were classified as high SES.

Procedure

An introductory letter was sent to Kano state secondary schools management to seek permission to conduct the study in twelve (12) selected secondary schools across the fourteen (14) educational zones in Kano state. A permission letter was giving, and distributed to all the selected secondary schools. The purpose of the study was explained to each principal of the selected schools, and consent forms were giving to students. A total of 520 students across the selected schools returned their signed forms (by their parents/guardians) and participated in the study. Each participant completed the SES questionnaire after thorough explanation on how to fill the questionnaire. Also, blood pressure, weight and height were all measured by the researcher or the research assistance. Any participant with BP greater than or equals to 133/92mmHg was considered hypertensive based on the findings of Balogun et al (1990).

Descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, and tables was used to summarize the data. The data was analyzed using inferential statics of Pearson product moment correlation, one-way ANOVA and Scheffe post-hoc at an alpha level of 0.05 with statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 15.

Results:

The results of the study are presented in the tables (Table 1, 2, 3, 4, 5)

The physical and physiological characteristics of all subjects are presented in a descriptive statistics of mean (X) and standard deviation (SD) (Table 1).

Table 1: Physical and physiological characteristics of subjects (N=520)

Variables	X±SD
Age	15.94±1.992
Weight	48.58±9.689
Height	1.55±0.103
Body mass index	20.10±3.030
Systolic blood pressure	121.33±12.607
Diastolic blood pressure	81.20±13.453

X ±SD = mean ±standard deviation

Table 2: Physical and Physiological characteristics of subjects by their SES class

Variables	SES	N	X±SD
Age (13-19years)	HSES	37	15.89±1.807
	MSES	326	15.83±1.958
	LSES	157	16.18±2.090
Weight (kg)	HSES	37	48.51±8.431
	MSES	326	48.68±10.338
	LSES	157	48.38±8.553
Height (m)	HSES	37	1.55±0.094
	MSES	326	1.54±0.105
	LSES	157	1.56±0.100
Body mass index	HSES	37	19.83±2.521
	MSES	326	20.27±3.180
	LSES	157	19.82±2.801
Systolic BP	HSES	37	115.00±9.428
	MSES	326	122.06±13.129
	LSES	157	121.31±11.769
Diastolic BP	HSES	37	77.84±12.722
	MSES	326	82.01±13.600
	LSES	157	80.32±13.213

Key: SES= socioeconomic status, HSES= high socioeconomic status, MSES= middle socioeconomic status, LSES= low socioeconomic status, BP= blood pressure.

Table 3: Correlation summary of SES by SBP and DBP

Variable	Blood Pressure	R	P
SES	Systolic Blood Pressure	-0.062	0.156
	Diastolic Blood Pressure	0.004	0.935

R(518)= 0.062; p<0.05

Table 4: ANOVA summary table on systolic and diastolic BP by SES class.

Variables	SES	N	X±SD	F	P
Systolic BP	HSES	37	115.00±0.428	5.290	0.05
	MSES	326	122.06±13.129		
	LSES	157	121.31±11.769		
Diastolic BP	HSES	37	77.84±12.722	2.091	0.125
	MSES	326	82.01±13.600		
	LSES	157	80.32±13.213		

F(2,517), P<0.05.

Key: BP= blood pressure, SES=socioeconomic status, HSES= high socioeconomic status, MSES=middle socioeconomic status, LSES= low socioeconomic status.

Table 5: Scheffe Post-hoc for systolic blood pressure across SES classes

SES classes	Mean Difference	P
Low SES Vs Middle SES	-0.749	0.829
Low SES Vs High SES	6.306*	0.023
Middle SES Vs High SES	7.055*	0.005

Key: SES= socioeconomic status

The physical and physiological characteristics of subjects in respects to their SES classes are presented in a

descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation in table 2 (Table 2).

To compute for relationship between SES and blood pressure (systolic and diastolic BP), Pearson product moment correlation was used as presented in table 3 (Table 3). Table 3 showed that no significant relationship ($r = -0.062$, >0.05 and $r=0.004$, $p>0.05$) exist between systolic and diastolic BP.

One-way ANOVA was used to test if SES will not significantly influence BP (systolic BP and diastolic BP) among teenagers in Kano state as presented in table 4 (Table 4). Table 4 shows that a significant difference ($F=5.290$, $P<0.05$) exist on subjects SBP and SES classes. However, the exact SES class where the difference exists is not known, therefore, Scheffe post hoc was computed across the SES classes as presented in table 4 (Table 4).

Table 5 shows there is significant mean difference of SBP between low and high SES classes ($MD=6.306$, $P<0.05$), and between middle and high SES ($MD= 7.055$, $P<0.05$).

Discussion

The main objective of this study was to determine the influence of socioeconomic status (SES) on blood pressure (BP) among teenagers in Kano state. A total number of 520 students from 12 selected public secondary schools in Kano participated in the study. Among the 520 participants, 37 (7.1%) were in high SES, 326 (62.7%) were of middle SES and 157 (30.2%) were in low SES. This is similar with the findings of Balogun et al (1990) in their study on influence of parental SES on casual BP of Nigerian school children, where they found that most urbanites belong to middle SES [11].

A significant influence of SES on SBP ($F=5.290$, $P<0.05$) among the participants was found, with higher SBP among the middle SES (122.06 ± 13.129). This finding is in contrast with the findings of Colin-Ramirez et al and Grebla et al who found higher SBP in low SES [19, 20]. Also, the finding differs from the finding of Bunker et al who found higher SBP occurrence in high SES [21]. The differences in the above mentioned studies results might be due to different geographical locations or due to the differences in the hypertensive cut-off point used in the studies.

A non-significant influence of SES on diastolic BP ($F= 2.091$, $P>0.05$) among the participant was found. Similarly, a non-significant relationship between SES and BP (SBP and DBP) was found ($r=0.062$, >0.05 & $r=0.004$, $p>0.05$ for SBP and DBP respectively). This study is in contrast with that of Miller and Shekele [1], and Wens, Hanull and Drizd [22] who reported an inverse relationship between parent SES and BP of their children. A direct relationship between SES (education and occupation)

and BP was found by Khoury, Morrison, and Laskarzewski [23] which is also different from the findings of this study.

Conclusion

From the study results, it can be concluded that socioeconomic status has an influence on blood pressure (systolic blood pressure). It is recommended that SES should be considered while assessing teenage patients.

References

1. Miller RA., Shekelle RB. Blood Pressure in Tenth Grade Students Result from the Chicago Heart Association: Paediatric Heart Screening Project. *Circulation*, 1976; 54: 993-1000.
2. Faisal A., Khaldoon A., Paul MM. Relation of High Blood Pressure to Glucos Intolerance, Plasma Lipids and Educational Stock Status in an Arabian Gulf Population. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 2000; 129 : 71-76.
3. Wolf-Maier K., Cooper RS., Banegas JR., Giampad S., Hense H., Joffres M., Katarinen M., Poutter N., Primates P., Rodinguez AF., Stegmayr B., Thamn M., Tuomilehto J., Vandzzo D., Vescio F. Hypertension Prevalence and Blood Pressure Levels in 6 European Countries, Canada, and the United States. *JAMA*, 2003; 289: 2363-69.
4. Carretero OA., Oparil S. Essential Hypertension Part 1 : Definition and Etiology. *Circulation*, 2000; 101(3): 329-35.
5. Karen TU., Zhongliang C., Lorraine LL. Prevalence and Incidence of Hypertension from 1995 to 2005: A Population Based Study. *Journal of Canadian Medical Association*, 2008; 178 (1): 1429-35.
6. Wamala SP., Wolk A., Orth-Gormer K. Determinants of Obesity in Relation to Socioeconomic Status among Middle Aged Swedish Women. *Prev Med*, 1997; 26(1): 734-44.
7. Lang T., Degoulet P., Aime F., Devvries C., Jacquinot-Salord MC., Fouriaud C. Relationship between Alcohol Consumption and Hypertension Prevalence and Control in a French Population. *Journal of Chronic Disease*, 1987; 40: 713-20.
8. Van Rossum CT., Van de Mheen H., Wittman J.C., Hofman A., Mackenbach JP., Grobbee DE. Prevalence, Treatment, and Control of Hypertension by Sociodemographic Factors among the Dutch Elderly. *Hypertension*, 2000; 35: 814-21.
9. Braunwald E. *Heart Disease. A Text Book of Cardiovascular Medicine* vol 1. Philadelphia: W.B. Saunders Company.
10. Anderson A. Hypertension in Children: An easier Method of Identification. *Paediatrics*, 2009; 123: 972-74.
11. Balogun JA., Obajuluwa VA., Olaogun MO., Aberejo OK., Oyeyemi AY., Adeodu OO., Balogun MO. Influence of Parental Socioeconomic Status on Casual Blood Pressure of Nigerian School Children. *International Journal of Cardiology*, 1990; 29: 63-9.
12. Vega LS., Agusti R., Ramirez JP. The Investigators of the Tornosol Study Factores de Riesgo de Las Enfermedades Cardiovasculares en el Peru. *Revista Peruana de Cardiologia*. XXXII: 82-128.
13. Ikeme AC. Blood Presssure and Hypertension in Nigeria: the Implication for Hypertension Control. *Tropical Cardiol*, 1987; 139(suppl II): 77-81.
14. Karaye KS., Okhialam BN., Wali SS. Plasma Lipids in Nigerins with Systemic Arterial Hypertension. *Journal of Clinical Lipidology*, 2008; 2(4): 274-78.
15. Morris S., Caeletto J., Hoddinott., Christiana LJ. Validity of Rapid Estimates of Household Wealth and Income for Health Surveys in Rural Africa. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 2000; 54: 381-87.
16. Grutto L., Huerta M., Sharabi Y. Hypertension and Socioeconomic Status. *Curr Opin Cardiol*, 2008; 23(4): 335-9.
17. Akinkugbe OO., Akinkugbe FM., Ayeni O., Solomon H., French K., Minear R. Biracial studies of Arterial Pressure in the First and Second Decades of Life. *British Medical Journal*, 1977; 1: 1132-37.
18. Oviasu VO., Alakija W., Oyarebu KA. Differences in Arterial Pressure and Body Build in the First and Second Decades of life in Urban and Rural Nigerians. *Tropical Cardiol*, 1981; 7:161-64.

19. Collin-Ramirez E., Castillo-Martinez L., Orea-Tejeda A., Villa AR., Vergara AC., Asensio EL. Waist Circumference and Fat Intake are Associated with High Blood Pressure in Mexican Children. *Journal of American Diet Association*, 2009; 109(6): 996-1003.
20. Grebra RC., Rodriguez MD., Borrel LN., Pickening TG. Prevalence and Determinants of Isolated Systolic Hypertension among Young Adults. *Journal of Hypertens*, 2012; 28(1): 15-23.
21. Bunker CH., Okoro FL., Markovic N., Thai N., Pippin B., Ackrell M., Kuller LH. Relationship of Hypertension to Socioeconomic Status in a West African Population. *Ethn Health*, 1996; 1 (1): 33-45.
22. Wens NS., Hanull PV., Dridz I. Blood Pressure levels of Children 6 to 11 years in Relationship to Age, Sex, and Socioeconomic Status. *Vital Health Status*, 1994; 11: 1-24.
23. Khoury PR., Morrison JA., Laskarzewski K. Relationship of education and Occupation to Coronary Heart Disease Risk Factors in School Children and Adults: the Princeton School District Study. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 1981; 113: 378-95.

Corresponding Author:

Farida Garba SUMAILA
Address: Department of Physiotherapy,
Bayero University Kano,
P.M.B 3011 Kano, Nigeria
Email: fareedat2006@gmail.com
fgsumaila.pth@buk.edu.ng
Phone: +2348036164228

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.